

Shop names and language culture: A study of linguistic landscape in Aceh's Tourist Hub

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The influx of tourists alters language culture, particularly in public signage, reflecting linguistic shifts, especially in Peunayong, a tourist hub in Banda Aceh, Indonesia. This study examines language use and its correlation with shop names and tourism in this area. Data from 81 shop names and 10 shop owners were collected through photographic documentation and a questionnaire. The results on the monolingual shop names reveal that English dominates at 32% of shop names, followed by Indonesian at 21%, and Acehnese at 4%, showing an evolving linguistic landscape amidst globalization. Bilingual (43%) and multilingual (1%) shop names embrace diversity and cultural heritage. Factors shaping these names include linguistic, commercial, and cultural aspects, with foreign influences recognized for their appeal. However, opinions on their prestige vary. Owners strategically choose names to attract customers, match their products, convey luxury, and display the local culture. Therefore, it is necessary to balance English dominance to preserve local identity.

Keywords: Attitude; Ideology; Landscape; Language Policy; Language Vitality; Panopticon; Power Dynamics; Shop Names; Sociosemiotics; Text

1. Introduction

Aceh, located in the far west of Indonesia, has emerged as a favored destination for both domestic and international tourists, spurring the growth of its tourism sector, especially in the capital city, Banda Aceh. Over the past three years, the number of domestic tourist trips to Aceh significantly increased, as reported by the Indonesian Central Statistics Agency (Badan Pusat Statistika, 2023). The figures indicate a notable rise in tourism activity. This upsurge in tourism has created concerns about language issues as language plays a crucial role in

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shaping tourists' experiences in the travel industry. Needless to say, effective communication between tourists and local communities, facilitated by appropriate language use, can greatly influence tourists' perceptions of a destination and foster a deeper understanding of its local culture and heritage (Kumar, 2017).

Despite theoretical expectations suggesting that the growing influx of domestic and foreign tourists to Aceh should not impact perceptions of tourist destinations, empirical evidence suggests otherwise. In reality, the surge in tourism can significantly influence the linguistic landscape of an area, particularly in public spaces such as signs, banners, advertisements, and writings (Halim & Sukanto, 2023; Mansoor et al., 2023; Napu, 2024), especially in prominent tourist areas such as Aceh.

The study of linguistic landscapes offers valuable insights into sociolinguistics by extending its focus beyond just groups of people to the spaces they inhabit. Blommaert (2013) posits that physical spaces are filled with social, cultural, and political dimensions, reflecting codes, normative expectations, and traditions—cf. Salmani Nodoushan's (2021, 2023) descriptions of 'text', 'panopticon' and 'sociosemiotics'; see also Eco (1968, 1986), Foucault, M. (1970, 1997), Landowski (2005), and Marrone (2021). Physical spaces also act as domains where power dynamics are influenced by human actions. Thus, examining the linguistic landscape offers various societal aspects such as language policy, ideology, power dynamics, language vitality, and attitudes. This perspective is echoed by Shohamy and Gorter (2009), who argue that the use of different languages on signs, particularly in business and institutional signage, reflects the strength, status, and economic role of these languages in a given region.

Previous research by Budiarsa and Kristianto (2018) examined language use in the public space of Bali, Indonesia, focusing on the evolving language symbols in tourist sites. Their findings highlighted a shift from local to global linguistic symbols, attributed to the increasing influence of tourism, requiring greater English proficiency among the local people. Although Balinese and Indonesian are official languages in Bali, English is becoming increasingly practical for tourists, overshadowing local languages. Likewise, Fakhroh & Rohmah (2018) explored the linguistic landscape of Sidoarjo, Indonesia, revealing Indonesian as the dominant language, and English being a more prevalent foreign language than Arabic. Despite Javanese being the mother tongue of most residents, its presence in the linguistic landscape is minimal, raising concerns about the representation of local languages in public spaces. Furthermore, da Silva et al. (2021) provided an overview of language usage, preferences, and informativeness in Malioboro, a prominent tourist destination in Yogyakarta. Their findings revealed the dominance of

Indonesian and English in commercial, regulatory, and infrastructure signage, revealing the 'linguistic landscape' (or LL) of Yogyakarta and its implications.

The cities studied by Budiarsa and Kristianto (2018), Fakhroh and Rohmah (2018), and da Silva et al. (2021) are considered municipal areas in Indonesia. Thus, in the present study, we looked at this phenomenon in smaller cities in this country, such as Banda Aceh. By exploring how the use of multiple languages in business signage contributes to creating an environment that embraces and respects linguistic diversity, this research aimed to deepen our understanding of the linguistic landscape, especially in the tourist hub of Peunayong in Banda Aceh. The findings can offer insights into the linguistic dynamics in similar cities while stressing the importance of preserving and promoting local language diversity as an integral aspect of the city's identity. Accordingly, the research questions for this study were:

1. What languages are preferred in the shop names in Peunayong, Banda Aceh?
2. What are the factors influencing shop names in this tourism area?

By focusing on how the linguistic environment influences the choice of shop names in a tourism area, this study sought to investigate how carefully selected shop names could reflect local culture and aid tourists in navigating their surroundings. The study was based on the assumption that understanding the language used in the tourism industry is vital for enhancing the tourist experience and supporting the local economy. By examining the impact of the recent surge in tourist numbers on perceptions of specific destinations, particularly in the linguistic landscape of Banda Aceh, this research attempted to bridge existing gaps in the literature.

2. Background

2.1. Linguistic landscape

Studies on linguistic landscape (LL) have been conducted worldwide for several decades. The term "linguistic landscape" was first coined by Landry and Bourhis (1997), who defined it as the examination and visualization of language in commercial signs and public spaces in specific locations. Backhaus (2007) further emphasized the importance of LL in discerning official from non-official signs. Considering demographic factors, such as race, is crucial when examining the LL, as historical and geographical circumstances influence the proportions of various ethnic groups (Albury, 2021).

Cenoz and Gorter (2006) emphasized the dictionary meaning of 'landscape', which implies both a physical extent viewed from a specific position and a visual extent of a natural landscape. Gorter (2006) applied these concepts

within LL studies, highlighting the thorough investigation of language in signs, crucial to understanding identity, cultural globalization, the prominence of English, and minority language revival. Ben-Rafael, et al. (2006) broadened the definition of LL to include any sign located inside or outside public institutions or private businesses in a specific geographical location. They proposed an inclusive definition covering signage both internally and externally within public institutions or private businesses in a designated area. This broader perspective aims to cover a comprehensive range of linguistic expressions and visual representations within a given geographical location. Accordingly, LL is a field of study that explores the relationship between language and landscape. This includes how landscape influences language and culture, the role of language in shaping cultural identity, and variations in language dialects influenced by local landscape and culture.

2.2. Functions of linguistic landscape

LL serves two functions: symbolic, and informative. According to Landry and Bourhis (1997) and Cenoz and Gorter (2008), the symbolic function relates to how language groups value and perceive the status of their languages relative to others. Meanwhile, the informative function can reveal their societal importance, linguistic repertoires, and the status of associated ethnic groups through the signs used by language groups (Backhaus, 2007).

Studying LL also helps identify the diverse languages spoken in a given area, as reflected in signage ranging from monolingual to multilingual. The dominance of one language over another in public signs indicates the strength and status of that language (Blommaert, 2010; Cenoz & Gorter, 2008; Leeman & Modan, 2009). Understanding the linguistic structure and sociolinguistic dynamics of a region is crucial for interpreting its LL.

2.3. Signs in public space

Public spaces have morphological, environmental, and aesthetic values and serve as urban generators and communication channels (Woolley, 2003). They facilitate social interaction, strengthening connections among individuals from diverse backgrounds (Zukin, 2010). Public spaces also contribute to mental health, human development, and collective identity formation (Shaftoe, 2008). These spaces hold different meanings for people based on individual experiences, social encounters, and cultural factors (Low & Lamb, 2000).

A sign is a fundamental element in semiotics (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021, 2023), representing something else within a semiotic field. According to Deely (2005), a sign comprises three essential components: (1) representation, (2) object, and (3) interpretation. And so, public signs, found in commercial and informational contexts, convey messages to the public. They take various

forms, such as signage, directions, advertisements, street names, shop names, signboards, and announcements (Halim & Sukamto, 2023; Mansoor, et al., 2023; Napu, 2024; Vinal, 2002). Ben-Rafael, et al. (2006) classify signs into top-down (official) and bottom-up (private) categories.

- Top-down signs are marks made by governments or other authorities. These signs often communicate official information, such as street names, traffic rules, and public service announcements.
- A bottom-up sign is a sign made by an individual or business. These signs are often used to advertise products or services or to express personal or political messages.

To conclude, top-down signs originate from governments or authorities, conveying official information, while bottom-up signs are created by individuals or businesses for advertising or personal expression. The diversity of bottom-up signs reflects community multilingualism and multiculturalism (Shohamy, 2006).

2.4. Previous studies

A number of studies have focused on LL. Besides studies in Indonesia (cited above), other studies worldwide have also focused on LL due to its role in promoting multilingualism and fostering more tolerant and inclusive societies. Hussein et al. (2015), for instance, examined language use on shop signs in Amman, Jordan, employing surveys and sociolinguistic questionnaires. His research revealed factors influencing language choice, particularly the prevalence of foreign names, predominantly English, in higher socio-economic areas. By the same token, Mansoor, et al. (2023) explored language diversity on shop signs across different regions in Malaysia, indicating a shift towards English predominance influenced by factors such as development and target market. Despite regulations favoring Malay, English emerged as the dominant language on signs.

Lu, et al. (2020) explored LL and language selection from the perspective of those immersed in it. Their study presents the transformation of Hongcun Village in China into a multilingual hub spurred by tourism development, where Standard Chinese characters dominate alongside traditional Chinese and English characters. Tourists acclaim the multilingual signage, viewing it as instrumental in shaping the image of the destination. While official signs adhere to a standardized format, private signs exhibit greater diversity, influenced by commercial motives rather than policy directives. Similarly, Zhang and Chan (2017) studied the multilingual LL of Macao, a bustling tourist hotspot. Their research discovered the relationship between traditional and

modern shop names, emphasizing their potential impact on the city's cultural and linguistic identity. Employing qualitative methods such as observation and interviews, the study offers valuable insights into language dynamics within a tourist-centric location.

In another study, Muriungi and Mudogo (2021) underlined the prevalence of English in the signages of Kenyan universities, constituting 77% of all signs. They attributed this percentage to the global recognition of English and the diverse student body in Kenyan universities. Nevertheless, Kiswahili and Arabic, the official languages, were notably absent from public signs, indicating a gap between language policy and implementation, imposing reform.

The findings from all of these studies, and similar other studies, highlight the dynamic nature of LL in various contexts, ranging from tourist destinations like Hongcun and Macao to academic institutions such as universities, and commercial hubs. The prevalence of English in signage reflects its global influence, yet the disparity between official language policies and their implementation may stress the need for more effective control of language use in public spaces. These studies show the importance of considering linguistic diversity and its implications for cultural identity, tourism promotion, and language policy formulation in diverse societal settings. Along the same lines, the current study sought to study examine language use and its correlation with shop names and tourism in Peunayong, Banda Aceh, Indonesia.

3. Method

3.1. Design

In this study, a descriptive qualitative method was employed. It outlines qualitative research as an exploration of problems, aiming to develop an understanding of phenomena through word-based data collection, analysis, and interpretation (Creswell, 2013).

3.2. Location

The location of this research is in Peunayong, Banda Aceh. Peunayong, historically renowned for hosting European and Chinese dignitaries during Sultan Iskandar Muda's era in Aceh (from 1607 until 1636), derives its name from *peumayong* in Acehnese, signifying 'protection'. Presently, it is esteemed for its culinary savors and unique Acehnese souvenirs. Micro, small, and medium enterprises line Peunayong Street, offering an array of products and services. The area's vibrant tourism scene is further heightened by the establishment of numerous hotels, facilitating accessibility for visitors and enhancing its appeal as an LL of interest. Two street areas in Peunayong were

selected for data collection: (1) Jl. Sri Ratu Syafiatuddin, and (2) Jl. Khairil Anwar (the green-lined area in Figure 1).

Figure 1.

The Map of Peunayong, and the Green-Lined Areas are the Focus of This Research as the Tourist Hub

3.3. Subjects

A total of 81 shops on these streets were sampled for the study. By using the bottom-up category (Ben-Rafaeral, et al., 2006), meaning private or individual or businesses, the shop names were observed. The criteria for selecting these shop names were based on their complexity and the variety of patterns observed in them. Franchise businesses, financial institutions, and distribution businesses such as hotels, banks, and offices were excluded. Then, 10 respondents, either owners or managers of the shops, were selected based on their availability and consent to fill in the questionnaires.

3.4. Instruments

The instruments for this research were documentation (photographs) and a closed-ended-and-open-ended questionnaire to capture the LL elements authentically and comprehensively. The questionnaire was constructed based on Hussein et al. (2015) and Mansoor, et al. (2023). These tools facilitate the exploration of language usage patterns and preferences among shop owners, thus enriching the qualitative analysis process.

3.5. Data collection

Documentation was done by taking photographs of the shop names (cf. Al-Na'imat, 2015), aiming to objectively represent language usage within the context. Following the documentation process, the language(s) used by the shop owners were categorized into various groups, facilitating a detailed language analysis within the observed context.

Closed-ended and open-ended questionnaires provide respondents with statements and written prompts to gather data. After acquiring sufficient documentation, the questionnaires were distributed to 10 shop owners to collect information about their attitudes, preferences, and opinions regarding the language used in their shop names.

3.6. Data analysis

Accordingly, the collected data were systematically organized based on these linguistic dimensions: (1) the dominant language in shop names, (2) the language utilized for shop names, and (3) the role of the language(s) used on shop signs. Each category was elaborated through descriptive paragraphs, followed by a detailed analysis to provide a comprehensive depiction of the acquired shop names.

4. Results

4.1. Languages preferred in shop names

The dominant category of language in the tourist area of Peunayong can be divided into three parts: (1) monolingual, (2) bilingual, and (3) multilingual. Table 1 shows the composition of shop signs in the area.

Table 1

The Dominant Language in Shop Names in Peunayong, Banda Aceh

Groups	Languages	No.	rounded %
Monolingual (46 names)	Indonesian	17	21%
	English	26	32%
	Acehnese	3	4%
Bilingual (33 names)	English and Indonesian	19	24%
	English and Acehnese	11	14%
	Arabic and English	1	1%
	Chinese and English	1	1%
	Spanish and English	1	1%
	Dutch and English	1	1%
Multilingual (1 name)	Indonesian-Acehnese-English	1	1%
Total		81	100%

As Table 1 shows, the monolingual part itself is further divided into three categories: Indonesian, English, and Acehnese. Moreover, bilingual shop names are divided into seven categories: English-Indonesian, Acehnese-Indonesian, English-Acehnese, Arabic-English, Chinese-English, Italian-English, Spanish-English, and Dutch-English. Meanwhile, multilingual shop names belong in only one category: Indonesian-Acehnese-English. From a total of 81 samples in this study, it was concluded that English is the most dominant language in the tourist area of Aceh, especially in Peunayong.

As seen in Table 1 (above), of the 81 ($N=81$) samples, 57% ($n=46$) exhibit monolingual names of Indonesian, English, and Acehnese languages. English dominates with 32% ($n=26$), emphasizing its global significance. An example in Figure 2 is the coffee shop named *Star King Coffee*; the owner explained that this name signifies aspirations of grandeur or excellence through the name 'Star King' on the taste of quality or a royal experience for customers of the original Acehnese coffee from Gayo highlands in the province.

Figure 2.

Some Examples of Monolingual Shop Names in Peunayong

Anyway, shop names in Indonesian remain crucial at 21% ($n=17$) for national communication and an example is *Toko Obat Sari*, literally translated as ‘essence medicine store’. It is a drugstore, and *sari* in this context refers to ‘essence’ or ‘extract’. The owner wants to convey the idea of providing essential or concentrated remedies, suggesting medicinal products that are the essence or extract of health and wellness. The least used category was Acehnese shop names at 4% ($n=3$). An example is *Peunajoh Aceh*; this is a souvenir shop that sells Acehnese traditional spices, food, and drink. Its name highlights its specialization in Acehnese cuisine, emphasizing authenticity and local pride by using the Acehnese word *peunajoh*, meaning food. Unfortunately, this finding reflects the diminishing history and culture of the Acehnese in naming their shop names in Acehnese words despite the linguistic landscape in general mirrors Peunayong’s evolution within global and local changes. It signifies English and Indonesian’s roles in business naming and daily interactions, particularly in tourism.

Figure 3.

Some Examples of Bilingual Shop Names in Peunayong

A total of 33 bilingual signs, facilitate interaction and convey essential information in both English and Indonesian. With 24% ($n=19$) of all bilingual signs utilizing English and Indonesian. One of the examples is *Mahkota Watch*; this shop sells watches and the name suggests prestige or quality associated with the word *mahkota*, meaning 'crown' in Indonesian, implying that the watches sold in the shop are of royal or superior quality. English-Acehnese bilingual signs at 14% ($n=11$) also play a significant role in promoting Aceh's cultural heritage to foreign tourists. One of the shop names in this category is *Ulee Kareng Coffee*. One of the coffee-producing districts in Aceh Besar is in the Ulee Kareng area (i.e., a district refers to an administrative division in Indonesia, which is below the provincial level); *ulee kareng* itself literally means 'the head (*ulee*) of a salted fish (*kareng*)'. By incorporating the name of the area known for its coffee, the owner seeks to highlight Aceh's cultural identity and attract tourists interested in experiencing authentic Acehnese coffee culture. Other bilingual names found are, Acehnese-Indonesian, Arabic-English, Chinese-English, Spanish-English, and Dutch-English; each stands at 1% ($n=1$). Though not many, these different shop names from Arabic, Chinese, Spanish, and Dutch in Aceh reflect their connection to Aceh through history, culture, and economy.

Multilingual shop naming appears less prevalent compared to the other categories; it comprises only 1% ($n=1$) of the total shop names in the Peunayong tourism hub. This suggests a minority presence of multilingual signs in this context. Figure 4 illustrates a multilingual sign incorporating Acehnese-English-Indonesian languages in the shop named *Kupi Atjeh Brownies*.

Figure 4.

Example of Multilingual Shop Names in Peunayong

During the colonial period and into the mid-20th century, the Dutch colonial administration commonly used the spelling *Atjeh* for Aceh in Indonesia. This spelling reflects the Dutch transcription of the Indonesian language at that time. While Aceh has become the standard spelling in today's Indonesian, *Atjeh* is still encountered in historical or traditional contexts. This is exemplified by this store name, bringing a sense of tradition or nostalgia by reminiscing about the historical Dutch colonial period when *Atjeh* was still used to refer to Aceh. This choice of spelling may aim to emphasize the region's heritage and cultural significance, particularly about modernizing the distinctive flavor of Acehnese (i.e., coffee) into the Western food, that is brownies.

4.2. Factors influencing shop names

4.2.1. Closed-ended questionnaire

Table 2 presents the results of a Likert-scale questionnaire aimed at understanding shop owners' preferences and opinions regarding their choice of shop names.

Table 2

Factors Behind the Choice of Shop Name Language (Rounded Percentages)

Motifs	1	2	3	4	5
Global impact of foreign culture	40%	30%	20%	10%	0%
Sounding more interesting	10%	40%	30%	20%	0%
Sounding unique and prestigious	0%	50%	20%	30%	0%
The type of goods sold	30%	60%	10%	0%	0%
Customers' level of education	10%	50%	40%	0%	0%

Note: 1=strongly agree, 2=agree, 3=undecided, 4=disagree, 5=strongly agree

The findings can be attributed to several factors contributing to the choice of shop names, with language playing a significant role. The motifs listed in the left column of Table 2 fall into two main categories: (1) linguistic factors, and (2) commercial and other factors.

Regarding linguistic factors, the data emphasize the influence of foreign cultures on language selection. Respondents strongly supported the significance of foreign cultures, with 40% 'strongly agree' and 30% 'agree'. Additionally, the presence of foreign names was deemed more attractive, with 10% 'strongly agree' and 40% 'agree'. However, opinions regarding the unique and prestigious nature of foreign names varied, with 50% 'agree', 30% 'disagree', and 20% 'undecided'. The data reflects diverse perspectives on the value of using foreign names.

On the other hand, commercial and other factors, such as (1) product type and (2) customers' education, also influence name selection. The majority of respondents (90%) agreed that the type of product significantly influenced their naming decision, while 60% believed that customer education level did not play a significant role. However, 40% expressed uncertainty about the relationship between customer education level and language selection. Thus, while there is general agreement on the importance of both linguistic and commercial factors, some respondents remain undecided.

4.2.2. Open-ended questionnaire

In this section of the open-ended questionnaire, the respondents were inquired about their opinions and reasons for using a particular language in their business shop name. The purpose was to gain a deeper understanding of why business owners choose specific languages for their shop names. Here are the main reasons provided by the respondents: (1) attracting customer attention and memorability, (2) type of goods sold, (3) introducing elements of luxury, and (4) familiarizing Acehese culture.

• Attracting customer attention and memorability

The first statement of the open-ended questionnaire reflected the shop owners' preferences for their reasons behind choosing their shop names. Nearly half of the respondents mentioned that giving a unique name to their shops could help attract customer attention. For instance, Respondent 1, an eyewear shop owner, implements marketing strategies to draw attention by using names or branding that reflect the uniqueness of the products offered.

Respondent 1: To attract customers and brand the store so that customers know we sell glasses

Respondents 2, 3, and 4 also aimed to grab customers' attention and entice curiosity about their offerings for easy recall. These shop owners sell products related to cellular devices and typical Acehese souvenirs.

Respondent 2: Because I want customers to be curious about what I sell, to attract customer attention

Respondent 3: To make it attractive and easy to remember

Respondent 4: To be memorable, and customers know we only provide pure coffee

From the respondents' statements, it is evident they want to create the impression that their shop names (1) make it easier for customers to

remember and (2) intrigue curiosity about their offerings. The suitability of the name to the goods or services also enhances recall and brand recognition among consumers, facilitating the process of brand recognition and fostering a strong connection between the shop and the customer. For example, Respondent 5, who sells various Acehnese souvenirs, incorporated his son's name into the shop's name to add a personal touch.

Respondent 5: The name of this shop is inspired by my child's name, as well as attracting customer attention

• Type of goods sold

In the business world, the name of the shop should perhaps align with the type of product or service offered. Respondent 6, who owns a shop selling a wide variety of watches, named *Mahkota Watch*, believes that the name should reflect the items sold, making it easier for customers to identify the types of products offered.

Respondent 6: Because it matches the items we sell, such as watches, the name of the store is automatically more suitable

Respondent 7: A name that fits my mind

Similarly, Respondent 7, a clothing business owner, emphasizes the importance of a suitable name in aligning with the type of products sold. Her shop, *Amanda Tailor*, sells clothes that are custom-made or offer tailoring services. It is named after a woman so customers know that the shop exclusively sells women's clothing. Choosing the correct name also helps create a consistent customer experience and reduces the risk of mismatches between customer expectations and the goods offered.

• Introducing elements of luxury

Selecting a name that conveys luxury is a strategic move to enhance the image and brand in the minds of consumers. Respondent 8, a coffee shop owner, chose a name that reflects the commitment to providing high-quality coffee with a sense of luxury.

Respondent 8: I want to prioritize the quality of the coffee made with luxury according to the name *Star King Coffee*

• Familiarizing Acehnese culture

Shop owners are often tasked with creating names that reflect and combine elements of local culture, support local identity, and attract customer attention.

Respondents 9 and 10, owners of a chicken porridge (*Bubur Kanji Ayam Bombay*, literally translated as 'porridge rice chicken Bombay') and souvenir shop (*Indatu Aceh Culinary*, literally translated as 'ancestors Aceh culinary'), aim to associate their names with the culinary affluence of the region to attract customer interest and promote authentic Acehese cuisine. The shop, *Bubur Kanji Ayam Bombay*, describes its menu, as offering *bubur kanji* 'porridge' with chicken seasoned with Bombay spices, likely to catch customers' interest. Meanwhile, *Indatu Aceh Culinary* sells traditional Acehese culinary specialties or snacks, often referred to as *oleh-oleh*, which are typically souvenirs or edible treats that people buy to bring back home from their travels.

Respondent 9: *Bubur Kanji Ayam* (chicken porridge) is a typical Acehese food; using that name can attract customers' attention and know [*sic*] exactly what I sell.

Respondent 10: Because it operates in the local culinary business sector, its name naturally aligns with the region, selling more or promoting the local Acehese culture.

Consequently, the reasons behind choosing specific languages for shop names vary, ranging from attracting customer attention to reflecting local culture and product characteristics. These considerations play a crucial role in shaping the identity and success of businesses in tourist areas like Peunayong. In this study, documentation results show that their definition of drawing the customers' attention is using monolingual English shop names, followed by Indonesian and Acehese as the least preferred. In terms of bilingualism, English-Indonesian names are mostly preferred compared to English-Acehese.

5. Discussion

After analyzing the data to identify the language choice in shop names in the linguistic landscape of tourism in Peunayong, Banda Aceh, a total of 81 shop names were detected, including monolingual, bilingual, and multilingual shop names. The first research question focused on identifying the dominant language used on shop names in this tourist area. This process involved classifying and tallying the data, revealing that English emerged as the dominant language in shop name choices within the linguistic landscape. In the monolingual category, 46 shop names are identified, with English being the most (32%), followed by Indonesian (21%), and the least is Acehese (4%). In the bilingual category, there are 33 bilingual shop names, with English-Indonesian the most (24%), followed by English-Acehese (14%); others at 1% each are Arabic-English, Chinese-English, Spanish-English, and Dutch-English. In the multilingual category, only one shop name was found in Indonesian-Acehese-English.

These findings highlight an interesting phenomenon where Indonesian, as the national language, and Acehnese, as the mother tongue, face significant transformations, indicating challenges to their Indonesian and Acehnese identity (cf. Aziz, et al., 2020; Aziz, et al., 2021; Yusuf, et al., 2022). The Indonesian language is currently experiencing great influences from English, posing contests to its preservation within its own cultural context. This phenomenon stresses the impact of globalization on Indonesia's tourism sector, with English emerging as a predominant language (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021). Despite regulations set by the local city council on permissible languages for signage (Mansoor, et al., 2023), the current study reveals a continued use of languages other than the national or local language of an area, reflecting the growing importance of English and other languages (Arabic, Chinese, Spanish, and Dutch) in Peunayong. Being "an uncharted territory of sociolinguistic and anthropological inquiry" (Salmani Nodoushan, 2024, p. 64), the diverse shop names in Arabic, Chinese, Spanish, and Dutch in Aceh reflect its historical, cultural, and economic ties with various nations. Since the 7th Century, Aceh has become a gateway for Muslim traders (Fatimah & Sari, 2017). These historical connections have left lasting linguistic and cultural imprints. Nevertheless, the widespread use of English, especially, in signage found in tourist destinations all over the world is now common (Hussein, et al., 2015; Mansoor, et al., 2023; Shang, et al., 2017) as English is treated as a global 'lingua franca'.

The impact of globalization on tourism in Peunayong, Aceh, is complex, presenting both positive and negative effects. Shohamy and Gorter (2009) contend that the use of various languages on signage, especially in business and institutional contexts, mirrors the (1) power, (2) prestige, and (3) economic significance of these languages within a specific area. In Peunayong, foreign tourist arrivals contribute to economic progress and improved welfare for local communities but they also pose a threat to local norms and traditions due to the influx of foreign cultural elements. Thus, preserving local cultural heritage faces new challenges in the context of globalization (Fakhroh & Rohmah, 2018).

The second issue addressed in this study pertains to the choice of language in shop names within Peunayong. It is revealed that foreign cultures strongly influence store name selection. The respondents acknowledged the value of foreign cultures and expressed interest in foreign names, consistent with findings from previous research (Hussein, et al., 2015; Mansoor, et al., 2023; Shang, et al., 2017). Business owners aim to attract potential customers by selecting unique and memorable names that arouse curiosity and distinguish their products (Aribowo, 2017; Prayoga & Khatimah, 2019). Factors influencing the decision to use foreign names include (1) perceptions of prestige, (2) positive attitudes towards foreign names, (3) commercial

interests, (4) product types, (5) customer education levels, and (6) financial considerations. These findings emphasize the importance of unique and memorable names in branding and marketing. In addition, incorporating elements of luxury into store names was identified as a strategy to (1) enhance brand image and (2) stand out from competitors. The majority of shop owners believed that signage in English conveys elegance and creates a premium image. This shows the significant impact of brand image on consumer purchasing decisions (Jahroni, et al., 2021).

Consistent with previous research by Gurusinga et al. (2023) and Saputri and Setiawan (2019), some shop names were incorrect in terms of grammar and spelling if they were in English, such as the shop names of *Foto Copy* (a print shop; the correct version in English: Photocopy), *Ipah Moudiste* (a women's tailor shop; the correct version in English: Ipah Modiste). Attention to proper language use is crucial to avoid confusion and misinterpretation in signage and banners. Adequate language use facilitating effective communication between tourists and local communities can significantly shape tourists' views of a destination and cultivate a richer appreciation of its local culture and heritage (Kumar, 2017).

6. Conclusion

The language preferences observed in shop names in Peunayong, Banda Aceh, reveal a complex relationship between linguistic diversity and cultural influences. English emerges as the dominant language, featuring in 32% of the total samples, followed by Indonesian at 21%, and Acehnese at 4%. This dominance displays the evolving linguistic landscape of Peunayong amidst globalization, where English serves as a vital means of communication, both nationally and internationally. Bilingual signs, comprising 43% of the total, demonstrate Peunayong's linguistic diversity and its efforts to envelop diverse audiences. Meanwhile, although less prevalent, multilingual signs signify an attempt to preserve Aceh's cultural heritage and linguistic richness.

All in all, the factors influencing shop names in Peunayong are multifaceted, encompassing linguistic, commercial, and cultural considerations. The survey findings highlight the influence of foreign cultures on language selection, with respondents recognizing the attractiveness of foreign names. However, opinions regarding foreign names' unique and prestigious nature vary, reflecting diverse perspectives among business owners. Additionally, factors such as product type and customer education level also play significant roles in name selection. Business owners strategically choose names to (1) attract customer attention, (2) align with the type of goods sold, (3) convey a sense of luxury, and (4) familiarize customers with Acehnese culture. These considerations underline the importance of linguistic and cultural sensitivity

in business branding and reflect the dynamic connection between language, identity, and consumer preferences in tourist areas like Peunayong. Nevertheless, there is a need to control the dominance of English to preserve the Indonesian and Acehnese identity in the tourism hub of Peunayong in Banda Aceh. Businesses can consider using English signage while also preserving local languages. Further research is recommended to explore the top-down aspect of language choices and address the limitations of the current study's sample size.

Authors' Statement

All of the authors had equal share in the writing of this paper. They discussed the idea of the paper together, and wrote it up with full collaboration. Professor Dr. Yunisrina Qismullah Yusuf took the responsibility of editing the final draft and then submitted the paper to the *International Journal of Language Studies* for review and possible publication.

Acknowledgments

We thank *Lembaga Penelitian dan Pengabdian kepada Masyarakat* (LPPM or Institute of Research and Community Services), Universitas Syiah Kuala, Banda Aceh, Indonesia, for funding this research, number 1702/UN11/KPT/2024.

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